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Making the Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies

DELIVERABLE 3.8 – PROTOTYPES FOR PRIVACY-RELATED QUESTIONS [FINAL VERSION]

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Executive summary

This deliverable finalises the work described in Deliverable D3.3: "Prototypes for privacy-related questions" (first version). It examines further the set of qualitative methods for analysing the key constructs which can be used for the understanding of privacy and ethics in extended reality (here and beyond - XR) technologies in the domain of Off-Highway Machinery (primarily - use cases of the project). Based on a two-step qualitative procedure involving end users and an online workshop with technology developers and use case stakeholders, we formulated and validated a set of quantitative measurements that can be taken to understand the space for ethics and privacy-related interventions in our and similar projects. The deliverable also presents the designed measurements with their preliminary diagnostic properties (Cronbach's alpha). In addition, the deliverable details the set of measurements we chose for the project's final evaluation, discussing the balance between determining the mainstream effects of the technologies on the perception of privacy and ethics, while keeping them concise enough to measure the effects of developed features without cognitive overburdening the participants. The deliverable is organised as follows:

- First, we explain the main theoretical concepts that motivated the development of elicitation and evaluation procedures; this section has been updated with additional sources that we have encountered since the previous version of the deliverable.
- Then we discuss the quantitative measures incorporated in the task-by-task evaluation of the final demonstrators, presented in the use cases, to identify perceived immediate threats to privacy in the full-scale working demonstrators, showing the project discussion about what the most suitable measures are for evaluating the demonstrators. We also describe a step-by-step procedure for using the selected methodology with the end users.
- We report the designed two-step methodology and the outcomes of the application of the method in all three use cases.
- After that, we explain in detail the constructs derived from the analysis of the recurrent themes mentioned in the focus groups and present them in connection with previous literature related to the domain of automation and the psychological effects of acquiring new technologies. We will also present the final scale we used for demonstrating the effects of potential design choices on users' acceptance of technologies. The results of the evaluation of the privacy concepts (N=264) and the privacy perception of the demonstrators (N=19) are presented in the deliverable D6.7.
- Finally, we explain methods we will use for assessment stage of the development of XR solutions.

Comparing to the previous versions of the deliverable we implemented main changes to the following sections:

- Section 1 (Introduction), expanded "Description of work" section (p.2)
- New section: 2.1.1 Value Sensitive Design in the development of XR technologies
- Section 3: the section structure has been reorganised
- New content in section 3.1.1 (all 3 workshops were conducted, provided information about participants)
- New section 3.2
- New section 3.3
- New section 3.4
- Rewritten section 3.7, which now shows the final set of used evaluation measures
- New Conclusion

The deliverable informs the privacy- and ethics-evaluating procedures, presented in the D6.7 Privacy assessment results.

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1 Introduction

In the current stage of the development of XR technologies, we see the continuous evolution from experimental prototypes to widely used solutions. The XR technologies are expanding from gaming and exploratory applications to various working contexts such as healthcare (e.g., [68]), industry (e.g., [19, 21, 76]), and education (e.g., [10, 38]). This integration of XR into the working environment helps users to model certain situations in virtual surroundings to predict and design actions required to address similar situations in the real world (e.g., employee training for extreme situations[76]); however the impact to real workplace integration is still mainly limited to the training purposes and visualisations of potential solutions (e.g., in architecture). Based on that, we can say that the current use cases of XR technologies at work have rather limited effects on the general workflow in the industries. At the same time, academics and industry stakeholders have pointed out that with further development and integration of these technologies, we can expect several groups of problems associated with the effects of this adoption on the privacy and ethics of work. The first group of problems is connected to the fact that XR technologies, while working, can capture a wide range of data [14]. This data can include physiological characteristics of the operator, such as the direction of movements of virtual controllers through haptic feedback devices or proximity sensors, or pupil delay through the eye-tracking system integrated into the VR headset. Some academic works discuss the joint application of VR and AI algorithms, presenting the opportunity to capture and combine physiological parameters and user actions. That, in turn, enables the system to make predictions about a person's mental state or the perceived difficulty of the task they encounter. This creates a new level of invasion of personal privacy, making the discussion about "mental privacy" in XR applications very relevant [3, 51]. It is important to stress that the use of XR devices affects not only the privacy of the initial user, but also the privacy of bystanders: people who are not using the XR-enhanced technology but are within the range of the device's data collection [51, 57]. They are usually unaware of ongoing data collection and, therefore, simply cannot opt out. To make the situation even more privacy-disturbing, previous works have also shown the opportunities to anonymise bystanders by linking captured data with external datasets, such as those provided by Facebook databases [35, 51].

Combined, the ubiquitous XR technologies, in conjunction with advanced AI data analysis, can significantly contribute to the state of total surveillance and pose serious personal privacy risks to both bystanders and users in the event of data leakage. However, privacy problems are not the only risks posed by XR technologies. As interactions become more realistic, it becomes very difficult to distinguish the exact boundaries between realities [63]. For instance, people might unintentionally confuse real and virtual objects and become overly dependent on these "extended" parts of reality to complete their tasks, which creates a risk of physical harm. Moreover, recent research has shown the possibility of exploiting these psychological mechanisms to deliberately manipulate users (so-called "human joysticks") to specific outcomes of interactions with XR for malicious purposes [12]. These two groups of risks are equally applicable to any application of XR devices. However, when implemented in a work environment, XR technologies pose additional risks to ethical and privacy-sensitive work surroundings. For example, as systems collect a lot of information about how users perform job-related tasks, is it ethical to use this data to evaluate performance and make promotion-related decisions? Can a person opt out of technologies that can enhance performance but are too privacy-invasive from a personal point of view? How can XR technologies be integrated into certain professions' workflow without making users pay too much attention to XR elements and neglect real-world signs?

To address these concerns, developers of XR-enhancement technologies for the workplace should develop ways to understand the relations between all players of the workspace in light of imbalanced power relations [41], as well as caveats which XR technologies can create for aggravating working conditions. The development group should adopt a design-for-privacy-and-ethics mindset and be able to assess any technology they plan to introduce from this perspective.

In the THEIA^{XR} project, we have adopted the co-creative privacy-by-design approach [79] from the beginning. First, we triangulated data from user interviews, workshops with developer stakeholders, and stakeholders' technology privacy-focused assessments to determine the project's starting points and privacy goals (described in D2.3). In the presented work, we outline the steps to create and validate procedures for continuing the privacy-sensitive development of technologies within the project. We approach it from the following positions:

On the Stage 1 (already presented in D3.3), we did the following:

- We created and tested the procedure of eliciting and discussing users' expectations from their work while using XR technologies. Connected to the main co-design procedure described in D3.2 and D3.4, we used the operator's persona and storyline of the problem scenarios to highlight the aspects of the work that are important for the workers and linked it to the developing technologies that can help them achieve their goals or, in contrast, create additional difficulties.
- We conducted interviews with industry experts in each of the Use Cases (UC) to establish the baseline of privacy and ethics practices in the industry and see how developers' and end-users concerns can be evaluated towards industrial standards.
- We created synchronous-asynchronous focus groups with the project's developers and stakeholders to re-evaluate the Privacy Requirements elicited in the previous stage of development and mark our progress toward achieving privacy goals.

On the Stage 2 (updates presented in the current deliverable), we did the following:

- We expanded the procedure of eliciting and discussing users' expectations from their work to the second stage, where we discussed what could happen with the working process if the chosen work-related values are not respected. We also complete both stages of the described procedure in all three of the project's use cases.
- Based on the findings of this procedure, we created a framework for complex evaluation of the potential ethical and privacy concerns of the operators in the off-highway machinery domain. We created the evaluation framework and formalised it in the form of a questionnaire. We calculated Cronbach's alpha and factorial dimensions reduction procedures [47,60] for all the scales, showing the instrument's consistency for future evaluations within the domain. We tested the selected user-oriented concepts of XR implementations with the end-users in off-highway machinery domains (the results of evaluation presented in D6.7).
- We pretested the procedures and validated scales mentioned in the previous versions of the deliverable aimed to be used in the course of detailed task-by-task evaluation, and found several problems associated with complex privacy measures in the out-of-real industrial work scenarios. We updated the evaluation questionnaires accordingly. The results of task-based evaluation are presented in D6.7

2 Methodology

2.1 Co-design methodologies for ethics and privacy

The THEIA^{XR} project adopted a transdisciplinary co-design approach and planned to invite the end users and other stakeholders to participate in each stage of the development and evaluation process from the very beginning of the project. This approach is part of the family of participatory and co-design methodologies developed within the European tradition of social engagement and designing for social good [11]. An important part of the methodology is its practical orientation and focus on talking with end users in their own language. This means that all abstract concepts of design should be translated into the practical form of scenarios and personas (fictional, but evidence-based stories about the workflow and workers' actions), to which end-users can relate [62, 65]. More detailed definition and explanation of the transdisciplinary co-design approach can be found in D3.2. Our approach to crafting the scenarios, examining work's ethics and privacy, was based on two key methodologies: Humanity-Centred Design (HCD) and Value-Sensitive Design (VSD). Humanity-Centred Design (HCD) is a concept proposed by D. Norman [54]. It is basically an extension of the concept of human-centred design [28] in the following dimensions: addressing the root problem (not just visible part of the problem), focusing on the ecosystem (e.g., how both the problem and solution relate to other socioeconomical processes and entities), taking a long-term systems perspective (how the things will evolve in time), continually testing and refining, and designing with the community as much as possible. Although the framework can be criticized for being too vague and general [30], we believe that addressing the future (beyond the research project) and evaluating the broader social outcomes of the designs for XR enhancement in industry can be useful because of the potential huge impact of the results in the domain.

Value-Sensitive Design (VSD) is an approach related to participatory design and is deeply rooted in ethical theories [26]. The main goal is to integrate a broad range of human values into the design of technology (from the start and through each stage of the design process). The approach suggests considering a broad range of values (e.g., fairness, justice, human welfare, and virtue [26]) and is widely used for projects that include multiple stakeholders and potential societal outcomes [8, 17]. The approach:

- stresses that researchers should specify and structure the values important to the end-users and other stakeholders in the project [39].
- acknowledges that the list of people affected by the designed technology is usually broader than just the end-users. Therefore, we need to focus on identifying possible stakeholders and addressing potential value conflicts between them [74]. This is done to create methods to resolve conflicts or organize values by priority.
- suggests starting by identifying project-specific needs. It can help with the prioritising process and determine the exact methodological instruments to apply [26].

The methodology includes various of design techniques [77] and methods [25] that allow for conducting conceptual, empirical, and technical investigations applied iteratively and interactively.

When applying VSD, we need to perform a conceptual investigation to a) identify and b) define the values implicated in a given design context. This includes to identify direct and indirect stakeholders, their values, and potential value conflicts. It also includes finding relevant ethical guidelines to relate them to our investigations. Empirically, the method applies interviews, surveys, observations, focus groups, and discussions with stakeholders to understand the use of existing technologies (and specify a baseline). The co-

design process would involve analysing the relationships between existing technologies, envisioned technologies, and users' values and needs to create a technological solution with the best value outcomes [26]. The approach applies across various social domains, including the design of technology for manufacturing [78], healthcare [81], the energy sector [44] and agriculture [29], among others.

VSD is also used to discuss the roles and values of social components of sociotechnical systems, e.g., operators' work. For example, Franssen [24] pointed to the fact that the role of operators in sociotechnical systems can be viewed as the tension between conformity to the rules (operators must follow specific instructions and rules) and autonomy (need to adapt to unforeseen circumstances). The work demonstrated that to design systems that respect operators' autonomy and clearly define their responsibilities (which, in turn, affect the reliability of the whole system), we need to account for values. [24]. Talking about the translation of high-level values into design recommendations, Van de Poel showed that it can be presented as a hierarchical structure [73]. This structure includes levels of abstract values, different kinds of norms (which he viewed as objectives, goals, and constraints), and specific requirements derived from the norms (see Fig. 1). He also mentioned that to create this value hierarchy from higher, more abstract ideas to practical recommendations, we can use both top-down and bottom-up approaches. In the latter case, we apply a "reverse-engineering" mindset to understand which values were in place to create certain design requirements and whether these bottom elements are the exact solutions needed to achieve the values we have in mind [73].

Figure 1: Three basic levels of value hierarchy, adapted from Van de Poel, (2013), with investigation directions

2.1.1 VSD in the development of XR technologies

Several papers explicitly discuss the VSD framework in relation to XR technologies. For example, in the framework of EU-funded project XR4Human, Voinov and de la Cruz Bernabe explicitly discuss the implications of VSD adoption for ethical XR development [80], creating actionable recommendations for designing XR technologies according to the VSD approach. Lim and Kim [45] combine a value-sensitive design approach

with other design frameworks to discuss the speculations and ethical design of futuristic technologies (including XR and AI). In their pioneering position paper, Friedman and Kahn [27] discuss that augmenting reality should acknowledge different facets of human experience (including understanding the boundaries between real and augmented objects and social interactions in mixed spaces) and advocate the use of VSD for clarifying the design space. From a practical point of view, [69] explored the case of designing a medical VR application using the step-by-step VSD methodology and argued for the benefits of this approach in design scenarios

2.2 Schwartz's Theory of Basic Values

VSD does not push for a specific way of settling the initial set of values for exploration [25]. The set of values can be high-level ethical values motivated by the topic of the design investigation, or they can be elicited explicitly through preliminary procedures (e.g., evidence analysis or discussing values with stakeholders). In our project, we decided to take the list of theory-grounded values proposed by Schwartz [66]. The original Schwartz approach proposes 10 key human values: benevolence, universalism, self-direction (autonomy), achievement, stimulation, hedonism, security, conformity, tradition, and power [64]. Schwartz described values as follows:

- they are closely tied with emotions, and people receive positive or negative emotional feedback when acting in line with or against their values;
- they are setting the standards for evaluating actions, situations, and people (e.g., as good or bad) and motivates people to take action.

It is also important to mention that Schwartz considered values as transcendent and applied in different contexts [66]. That means they are applicable to various aspects of everyday life, including work. For example, Cohen investigated the connection between values and organisational commitment and showed the connection between benevolence and commitment in employees; he also scored the perception of justice as an important factor of employee commitment [16]. There are several questionnaires dedicated to measuring the importance of each value and creating a hierarchy of values for a single person. The most popular forms are the Schwartz Value Survey (SVS) and the Portrait Values Questionnaire (PVQ40) [67]. There is also a short 10-item adaptation proposed by Lindeman and Verkasalo [46]. However, Albrecht et al. mention that to understand values in a work context, it is important to ask questions which specifically reflect the working setting (e.g., explicitly asking questions pointed to working situations). To address this, they proposed the Values at Work Scale [5].

2.3 Expanded Technology Acceptance Model

In addition to Schwartz's model, we applied a more utilitarian set of parameters, which can help to quickly weigh particular technological implementations or features. We based our approach on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) [18], which we interpreted as the alignment of the features of the XR implementations with the user's practical/utilitarian values. We also used some enhancements of the TAM model from the Value-based Adoption Model (VAM) [37]. We incorporated the values of safety and excitement, which are theoretically proven to be important in the concept of engineering development and specifically XR. TAM is a widely used model that aims to predict users' attitudes toward using technology by assessing two predictive factors: perceived usefulness (which, in our work, we can view as utility value) and perceived ease of use (respectively, accessibility value) [49]. The VAM interprets the items of TAM in the

frames of values. VAM incorporates the concept of enjoyment as a core value that affects the adoption of new technology [37]. A survey conducted by Chuah showed that enjoyment plays a significant role in the structure of XR adoption across multiple XR applications [15]; Lee et. al even mentioned enjoyment as better prediction of VR adoption than usefulness and other utilitarian qualities [43] Enjoyment is also mentioned in the discussion about the research agenda of industrial XR applications [34]. Finally, we decided to incorporate security/safety concerns into our explorative model. We did it for the following reasons: first, the security and safety values play one of the core roles in the discussion of Engineering Values proposed by van de Poel [75]. It is also shown that notions of privacy and security risks in Extended Reality are shared between users and experts [2, 4, 31, 32, 56]; that means we'll have a common ground to discuss it with the end-users.

3 Development of Elicitation and Evaluation Procedures for Privacy and Ethics-Related Questions

The procedures described in this section were built upon the previous privacy-related investigation procedures discussed in D2.3. They were also connected with the work described in D3.2, as all the scenario-based elements used in our procedures were tied to the main storylines of the scenarios and features, co-elaborated during the ideation phase of the transdisciplinary scenario-based co-design approach.

3.1 Stage 1: Elicitation of basic ethical values of operators using an adapted short version of Schwartz’s Theory of Basic Values questionnaire in the working context and creation of working personas

We started our procedure by creating a suitable list of values for further integration. Albrecht et al. [5] successfully integrated the Schwartz values in the context of work. However, their approach, which consists of 52 items, may be overly long for presenting concepts to operators. In our work, we created a short, 10-item version of the questionnaire based on the conceptual work and formulations of Albrecht et al. [5]. Our goal was to create a concise conceptual description, similar to the brief version of the original Schwartz instrument developed by Lindeman and Verkasalo [46]. The result is a brief questionnaire that presents the main values of Schwartz’s theory, and respondents are asked to rate the importance of each value in their work. Since the goal of this stage was not to validate the questionnaire, it was used merely as an instrument to help users better understand the Schwartz model for subsequent values-related discussions. Some of the short concepts were later incorporated into the final evaluation set.

Table 1: Short questionnaire for understanding Schwartz values in working context.

How important is it to you that your job...:							
	1 (extremely unimportant)	2	3	4	5	6	7 (extremely important)
offers clear opportunities for success and recognition (e.g., you can achieve career advancement, promotions, etc.).							
offers substantial personal pleasure and opportunities for enjoyment (e.g., you can experience pleasurable activities or have fun during work).							
involves a dynamic and challenging environment that keeps you engaged (e.g., your work includes a variety of tasks and challenges).							
allows for autonomy and creativity in your tasks and projects (e.g., you can make your own decisions and set priorities at work).							
contributes to broader societal goals like environmental sustainability or social justice (e.g., your work helps make the world a better place).							

operates in a supportive and caring team environment where you can trust and help your colleagues (e.g., your job allows you to support and collaborate with the people you meet at work).							
respects and incorporates cultural or corporate traditions (e.g., in this job, you can work according to your values or within a company that shares your approach to work).							
emphasizes following rules and respecting authority (e.g., you work in a group where everyone supports the organization's policies and rules).							
provides stability and security in a well-organized environment (e.g., you perform your work in a safe and secure space; the company prioritizes security).							
provides you with a position of influence and authority (e.g., you can decide who does what, command other people and resources).							

3.1.1 Placement of XR enhancement ideas into the dimensions of core and utilitarian values

Based on Van de Poel's [70] hierarchical approach to go from Values to Design Requirements and in the opposite direction (using Requirements to understand Values better), we proposed a first Value-Centred co-design workshop for the operators. The workshop has the following structure:

We started by explaining to the operators what VSD is and why it can be useful to keep values in mind while designing for workplace applications. We discussed the values beyond their work and which of them best align with the operator's profession (specified for each use case). When we specifically discussed the ideas that emerged from the ideation phase of transdisciplinary co-design, focusing on usefulness, safety, enjoyment, and ease of use. Then we showed the operators the list of original Schwartz values and pointed out that values can be used in different contexts, including the context of work. To familiarise the operators with the values, we asked them to fill out the questionnaire described in the previous section. We emphasised that we were not collecting this data and that operators would keep it for their own purposes (an example of persona presented in Figure 2¹). We discussed what the core values of the operators' profession are, which personal values can help them to achieve success in this job and which are less important. We specifically pointed out that the set of Schwartz values is just a starting point, and the operators can propose their own concepts. To make the ideation easier, we proposed a persona of fictional operator (already used in the investigations described in 3.2). This operator had a long and successful career, and we asked which values probably helped this person to maintain this long and productive professional life. Each participant created their own list of value hierarchy separately; then we asked operators to share their insights with colleagues and researchers to see how closely their opinions aligned. By the end of the procedure, we expected to have a list of values important to operators in their daily work. When we presented a list of implementation ideas validated in previous stages of co-design and asked the operators to rate each idea based on four parameters: ease of use, usefulness, safety (including security and privacy risks), and enjoyment. As we were interested in discovering possible conflicts between values, we specifically pointed out that the same implementation could be beneficial in one parameter but detrimental in another

¹ The image of fictional operator Marco was generated by ChatGPT3.5 No partners information was loaded in the AI system

(e.g., making the work easier but more boring). Initially we applied the Sentence completion method [40], asking for the reason behind the assessment, however in the UC2 and UC3 workshops we shifted to free form discussion, as it gave us more rich information. After that, participants discussed the conflicts and trade-offs among the features with one another and with the researchers.

We pretested the workshop structure internally with 3 participants at the University of Luxembourg to identify the main pitfalls of the method and made some adjustments. We then conducted three workshops within the investigations of UC1 (6 participants, including 3 operators Mean (hereafter M) = 44.3, Standard Deviation (hereafter SD) = 12.7), UC2 (3 operators, M = 49, SD = 7, 1 participant preferred not to answer; M years of experience = 26.33, SD = 7.10), and UC3 (7 operators, 1 operator prefer not to answer, M = 39.5, SD = 11.83, M years of experience = 18.67, SD = 15.13). All participants were male operators.

During the UC1 workshop, we observed that going through all the features is exhausting for the operators and deteriorates the quality of the discussion. To address this, for the workshops in UC2 and UC3, we proposed choosing the features for discussion that they perceived as most useful and/or most controversial. We decided that this approach would help to focus on the most problematic areas. Based on all three use cases, we specify the complete list of concepts, which can be taken for further exploration: perception of autonomy, risks of over-reliance, worries about safety (including distractive effects of the features), effects of the new technologies on workplace communication, skill perception and detachment of workers from their work. As in most cases, it was difficult to disentangle the concepts from each other, and we decided to proceed with the second workshop to clarify which values related most seriously to the concerns and how operators see the way to fix the concerns while implementing the features.

Let's try to adapt these values to your work

What values should a person embrace to succeed as a **snow groomer** operator?

Marco, *experienced operator with long and successful career*

Figure 2: Introduction of the fictional persona of Marco, the snow groomer operator².

² Picture created with the support of AI

3.2 Stage 2: Verification of basic ethical values of operators using scenarios of values violation

For the series of the second workshops with operators (10 participants, 7 of them operators, M for operators 39.86, SD = 10.11, working experience 15.71, SD = 10.93), UC2 (5 operators, M = 45.67, SD=7.64, working experience M = 24.8, SD = 5.45) and UC3 (6 operators, M = 39.5, SD = 11.83, M years of experience = 18.67, SD = 15.13), we created a series of anti-scenarios: scenarios of future work, where the implementation of the XR solution leads to the contextual violation of the value. For example, in the case of autonomy value, we created a scenario in which the fictional operator became upset with these technologies, which made their work mechanistic and overly guided. The presented approach is related to the exploration of "what if" scenarios and negative outcomes of technology, which is a common method in VSD (e.g. [59, 72]):

- First, we presented to the operators the results of our previous discussion on the concept.
- Second, we asked operators how realistic they found the outcomes of the scenarios and what could be done to mitigate the adverse effects of the technology on future work. The operators discussed inside their groups and when provided their opinion.
- Based on the second workshop, we finalised a list of concepts for further quantitative exploration.

What if...

Independence of the operations

*I am NOT in
charge of my
work*

Marco is an **experienced** operator, having worked for many years with different models of snow groomers.

While he was initially happy to start using the safety and assistance system, he soon felt the urge to **switch it off** after several uses. **He finds it annoying that the system often tells him what to do, how to prepare the slope, and how to move the vehicle.** As someone who knows his craft, he feels the system's constant guidance is unnecessary, as he already knows better ways to do his job.

Figure 3: An example of value violation scenario

3.2.1 Qualitative findings based on the workshop series

We find the following recurrent ethical values in our workshops:

3.2.1.1 *Autonomy*

The area of work in the Off-Highway machinery domain can be very challenging and often requires the operator to act creatively and search for a unique way to perform the task within the confines of exact operation. While operators did not imply that their actions can be too creative up to the working norms violations, they mentioned that over restriction, overregulation and overguidance during the operation can

be perceived very negatively. Therefore, developers should avoid proposing any solutions that might be perceived as affecting the operator's autonomy (e.g., over guidance through the working procedure). Operators should play the main role in operation decision-making, and XR enhancements should just support autonomous work (e.g., suggesting actions without directing the procedural flow). One of the discussion points was that operators were ready to use the systems we discussed as long as they could be switched on or off at the operators' will. The inability to switch the systems on/off was perceived as unacceptable or slightly acceptable (only in case of critical safety in operations; but in this case operators imply that conflict should be minimal - they can't imagine an operator who deliberately will not use the helping system in critical conditions).

3.2.1.2 Over reliance

In relation to the previous points, operators often discuss the features as potentially provoking overreliance, especially in beginner operators with not enough experience to be able to make decisions themselves. In that case, operators proposed two lines of potential remedies. The first was related to the system itself: the system should periodically remind the operator to look outside the cabin and validate its decision by its evaluation. However, another group of operators in UC2 suggested that these reminders can create additional distractions and therefore will aggravate the situation instead of improving. They instead suggested putting more serious emphasis on the operator's education and training, including specific training on how to interact with XR features.

3.2.1.3 Sense of community and Communication

The sense of community was a tricky value to discuss in this job, as the operators usually perform alone. However, the operators mentioned higher-level relations with colleagues during the shift or after, which can be explained as supporting a warm atmosphere in the workplace. It is also worth noting that all the discussed jobs have a part of informal interactions during the performance of the job, e.g. discussion on how to take the slope collectively, or who comes to help another operator to finish the job in need. Therefore, the participants had mixed feelings about technologies impact on this domain; the most active concerns were presenting in UC2 in relation with distant operations.

3.2.1.4 Boredom and Engagement

The concepts of boredom and engagement stem from the importance of self-reflection and interest in the job, which, in the operator's opinion, is crucial to a long, productive life. As the discussed XR implementation to some extent made the work more predictable, we tried to understand to what extent we should consider boredom as a factor. We received these concerns from the operators in UC1 and especially in UC2, again in relation to the distant operation scenario. However, the operators also mentioned that as long as they are in control over using/not using the implementations, the problem of boredom is not the most problematic.

3.2.1.5 Distraction

In the discussion of security issues and overreliance, we received several comments from the participants. That distraction, created by the implementations can also become an issue. We specifically discussed it in UC3 in relation to the LED implementations, as some of operators mentioned that the bright colours around the windshield can be a problematic issue. It was less related to other implementations, however, in general operators mentioned the tendency to minimise the new systems and screens in their workplace as the operation space already provides a lot of information and it is difficult to prioritise the most important one.

3.2.1.6 Detachment

Another concept, which came after analysing the concept of involvement in work, was detachment. While firstly we proceed with it in relation to the boredom scenario, we realised that it is a separate topic, related to the general discussion about detachment in the XR community (e.g., [1, 9]). We thought it could be particularly problematic for the distant operation sub-case of UC2, as in this scenario the operator has minimum connections with reality. Operators confirmed our concerns and mentioned that the problem could be very real up to the point that people will operate with less care because of perceiving the situation as a game.

3.2.1.7 Skill Devaluation

The topic was specifically brought up in our discussion with UC3 operators, as they brought up the concerns that the implication of the new technologies can make the gap between more skilled and less skilled operator smaller and therefore affect professional development and workplace dynamics. These concerns very much reflect the general concerns workers have in the presence of new technologies, e.g., [13].

3.3 Finalised list of dimensions for exploration of ethical and privacy concerns in Industrial use of Extended Reality

Based on the synthesised results of the 2-step explorations in all three use cases, we came up with the number of constructs for the final exploration of privacy and ethics-related concepts in the projects. We first specified the constructs from our focus groups and related them to the concepts presented in the related literature. The constructs were discussed and refined by the project's working group at the University of Luxembourg. We also used Claude AI to refine the pull of items and evaluate final formulations (understandability) on various fictional operator personas; no project-related data was given to the AI system.

Here, we present a table of the final concepts along with the considerations and items for the final evaluation

Table 2: List of Constructs for evaluation

Construct	Definition	Based on	Final items for evaluation
Data storage concerns	Concerns related to the uncertainty, where and how the collected data will be stored and how they can be used for work evaluation or promotion	Adoption of IUIPC (Internet Users Privacy Concerns "Collection" scale, Malhotra et. al. [48])	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It bothers me when this [XR system] collects information about my work. • The fact that this [XR system] collects information makes me hesitant to use it. • It bothers me to give this [XR system] access to information about my work. • I am concerned that this [XR system] collects too much information about my work

Autonomy concerns	Concerns, related to the uncertainty where the system will respect the users' autonomy and give the users freedom to work in the way they prefer to	Conceptually related to Autonomy subscale of The Work Design Questionnaire [53]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>I believe, that presented XR system allow me to choose how to use this system while operating</i> • Limit my control over how I perform tasks • Give me freedom to use this system if I want to
Over reliance concerns	Concerns, related to the uncertainty where the system design will provoke user rely on it too much	Conceptually related to the Parasuraman's concept of Technological Complacency [58] Automation-induced complacency potential scale [52] and Trust in Automated Systems scale [36]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give me reminders to check what the system shows • Prompt me to stay alert to the situation • Give me cues to think critically about the information system provided
Collaboration concerns	Concerns, related to diminishing workplace interaction and communication, and, wherefore, human touch on the workplace	Conceptually based on Team Climate Inventory [6] and Need Support at Work scale (Relatedness subscale) [71]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce how much the operator needs to coordinate with team members • Support coordination or communication among coworkers • Maintain normal collaboration with colleagues
Boredom concerns	Concerns that the XR implementation will make work more boring	Conceptually related to workplace Dutch Boredome Scale [61]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make the work feel more repetitive • Make the work feel more interesting • Make the operation feel less engaging
Distraction concerns	Concerns that system provide information which can distract operator from the main task	Conceptually related to the literature on visual cluttering, cognitive load and alarm fatigue, e.g., [64]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add information that pulls my attention away from the main task • Make it harder to focus on what's most important • Create too many things to pay attention to at once

Detachment concerns	Concerns about detachment from real world and perception of the working process as less real	Conceptually related to dissociation and lower sense of presence because of use of XR, e.g., [1,9]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make the work feel less tangible and hands-on • Create a sense of distance between me and what I'm really doing • Make the work feel less direct and real
Skills Devaluation concerns	Concerns related to devaluation of the skills because the new system improve the performance of the beginners to the professional level	Conceptually based on the ongoing discussion about work skills replacement, e.g., [13] and similar concerns in AI domain [22]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make years of experience matter less for doing this work well • Reduce the advantage of being a skilled operator • Reduce how much operator actually use their skills while working

3.4 Psychometric properties and constructs validation

All the mentioned dimensions were put into the final evaluation questionnaire. We administered the mentioned questionnaire via an online vignettes-based experiment, with operators of different Off-Highway Machinery. The final dataset (after data cleaning procedures described in D6.7) consisted of 264 participants, 183 self-declared as male, 79 as female and 2 prefer not to disclosure the information, mean age was 36.69 (SD = 11.89), mean of declared experience with one of Off-Highway Machinery-related industrial domains (e.g., Forestry, Construction) is 8.16 (SD = 7.66) and mean of professional experience as operator is 4.79 (conservative estimates, as some participants with less than a year experience posted 0 in the form). The 186 participants reported experience with excavators, 91 with reach stackers, and 36 with snow groomers. In addition, 17 participants mentioned experience with Forklift/Lift Trucks, 12 - with tractors and farm equipment, and 7 - with loaders. 7 with other construction site equipment, 5 - trucks and haulers and 2 - with material handlers. To determine the psychometric structure of the designed scales, we calculated Cronbach's alpha [60] across each of the 3 presented XR implementations (based on the description and visual design of the solutions proposed in the project). We also applied Varimax rotation to the results of the designed questionnaire to check if the factor structure confirms the independence of the specified dimensions.

Based on our analysis, we found that two reverse-coded items (Autonomy(item2) and Boredom(item2)) significantly lowered the Cronbach alpha for the respective scales and loaded into the wrong factor in exploratory factor analysis. After deletion of the items, all the scales demonstrate excellent-to-good psychometric properties, as listed below.

Table 3: Cronbach's alpha for scales, values >.7 considered as acceptable

Scale	Cronbach's alpha (before items deletion)	Cronbach's alpha (after items deletion)
-------	--	---

Privacy (collection)	.965	.965
Autonomy	.712	.868
Overreliance	.804	.804
Communication	.704	.704
Boredom	.455	.787
Distraction	.884	.884
Detachment	.876	.876
Skill Devaluation	.928	.928

The effect of reverse coding on the lower reliability is discussed in the literature (e.g., [68]) however, it can also potentially be aggravated by the length of the study (which took a median of 23 minutes) as well as being settled in an online, less controllable setting. Therefore, we propose as follows: future works should continue non-reversed third items for the Autonomy and Boredom scales, as the 2-item scales are under ongoing debates of reliability properties [20]. At the same time, we suggest testing the reliability and validity of the instrument in a more controlled environment to receive additional estimates of the properties of the original forms of Autonomy and Boredom scales.

We implemented dimensions reduction procedure (Principle Component Analysis [46]) to check if the predicted dimensions are reflected to the factor structure of the questionnaire. Exploratory factor analysis using principal axis factoring with varimax rotation was conducted on pooled data (N = 739 observations (sum of all three vignettes by each of the parameters)). While Kaiser criterion and parallel analysis suggested 6 factors, we kept the theoretically justified 8-factor structure (73,3% of explained variance), as the 6-factor solution merged three conceptually distinct constructs (Boredom, Detachment, Devaluation). All three constructs appears in the end of the questionnaires and all have a negative connotation, which probably explain moderate intercorrelations. However, the mandatory 8-factors load demonstrated that the questions are correctly loaded into 8th factor structure with Detachment items slightly cross loaded in F2 and F3. In the future tests we suggest to spatially disentangle these three dimensions (e.g. put the detachment in the start of the questionnaire) or test random scales distribution in the questionnaire to crosscheck the order effect. The final rotation matrixes and factor structure presented in Table 4 and 5.

Table 4: Total Variance Explained

Factor	Total	Initial Eigenvalues		Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
		% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.556	32.853	32.853	7.323	31.839	31.839
2	2.847	12.379	45.232	2.607	11.335	43.175
3	2.535	11.021	56.253	2.292	9.967	53.142
4	1.648	7.166	63.419	1.349	5.863	59.005
5	1.487	6.466	69.885	1.212	5.271	64.276
6	1.236	5.372	75.257	.983	4.275	68.551
7	.940	4.086	79.343	.629	2.736	71.288

8	.684	2.974	82.317	.399	1.736	73.023
9	.561	2.438	84.755			
10	.444	1.930	86.685			
11	.379	1.647	88.332			
12	.356	1.550	89.882			
13	.333	1.447	91.329			
14	.307	1.336	92.665			
15	.296	1.288	93.953			
16	.250	1.087	95.041			
17	.225	.980	96.021			
18	.222	.963	96.984			
19	.205	.891	97.875			
20	.156	.676	98.551			
21	.130	.567	99.118			
22	.119	.516	99.634			
23	.084	.366	100.000			

Table 5: Rotated Factor Matrix

	Factor							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
A1	-.037	-.057	-.004	-.110	.843	.107	.016	-.002
A3	-.070	-.028	-.016	-.071	.887	.074	-.023	-.037
O1[r]	.025	.044	.003	.750	-.127	-.085	-.049	.018
O2[r]	.108	.058	.102	.799	.031	-.060	-.001	.019
O3[r]	.102	.078	.000	.712	-.076	-.078	.018	.023
C1[r]	-.011	-.110	-.120	.078	-.083	.497	-.267	-.029
C2	-.064	-.035	-.050	-.328	.200	.590	.053	-.047
C3	-.009	-.014	-.039	-.144	.150	.956	.026	-.027
B1	.111	.232	.217	-.042	.021	-.013	.680	.166
B3	.118	.283	.265	-.008	-.039	-.123	.722	.115
DS1	.168	.175	.753	.029	-.001	-.048	.200	.090
DS2	.160	.210	.838	.084	.006	-.087	.187	.060
DS3	.164	.247	.745	.013	-.026	-.080	.087	.214
DE1	.160	.365	.351	.006	-.037	-.064	.250	.520
DE2	.154	.380	.433	.102	-.043	-.104	.256	.525
DE3	.161	.454	.377	.090	-.043	-.073	.301	.554
DV1	.159	.774	.232	.104	-.036	-.051	.171	.210
DV2	.147	.903	.209	.079	-.033	-.070	.165	.040
DV3	.144	.812	.208	.070	-.048	-.045	.180	.132
SEC1	.901	.115	.138	.085	-.043	-.022	.062	.063
SEC2	.928	.115	.136	.083	-.052	-.023	.071	.077
SEC3	.924	.120	.121	.081	-.036	-.047	.053	.063
SEC4	.883	.127	.133	.074	-.022	-.007	.090	.037

Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

3.5 Evaluation of the industrial baseline for ethics and privacy

To properly pose the ethical and privacy concerns of the end-users into the broader landscape of the domain and to understand the relations between our solutions and the industrial baseline, we developed the structure for the semi-structured interview, following VSD practice of domain exploration [26]. Based on previous works in ethics/privacy in XR described in briefly in Section 1 and in more details in D7.6, we created the list of questions (Table 6). We tested the procedure with experts across all three use cases (3 experts in total). The results showed that the design ideas and implementations proposed in the project do not exceed the baseline in personal data collection. We also found that despite end users' concerns; only a small number of companies really use performance data of operators in work-related decisions. However, experts also confirmed that operators are usually passive about their data and have little initiative to ask for access to or data deletion when leaving the company. However, as one of the claimed goals of the project was to bring more data to the operators and to collect the data for making their analysis (for work enrichment purpose), we need to be careful if these concepts will be implemented in final version of the solutions, as they will greatly exceed current data collection status quo and can provoke strong reactions from stakeholders and end users of the company.

Table 6: Semi-structured interview, for establish baseline for privacy and ethics on workplace (use cases domains)

Does the vehicle collect (or can potentially collect, e.g., the feature exists in the new vehicles but was not present in the older models) **some types of information such as:**

- GPS data
- data about the speed of movement and directions of the movement
- environmental conditions (like temperature, moisture)
- (any) obstacle information through sensors or cameras (e.g., position of other objects nearby), borders of operation site
- operational efficiency metrics (e.g., fuel usage)
- safety-related data (proximity alerts and collision warnings)

If any of that is collected, where and how this **information is typically stored**? **How long** is it **usually stored**? If there any additional rules for longer storage in case of incidents?

How does **authorization for vehicle use** occur, step-by-step? **Where is the authorization data stored**?

How is access to the **data typically managed**? Has the company considered scenarios where operators request access to their data (if you ever heard about these types of requests)? If so, what types of data might they inquire about?

Does the **vehicle monitor any vital signals from the operator** (e.g. fatigue levels/ alertness through eye tracking)? If yes, where does the information store?

If the **operator leaves the company**, what **usually happens to the data associated with them** (e.g., performance data, if they are collected)?

Have the companies usually implemented any **analytical approaches** to the data? Do the data used for promotion/salary decision? Do the data use for **other purposes**, e.g. **AI models training**?

If there are any **standard consent forms** in the industry, explaining the operators GDPR related issues connected to their work, or each company implement their own forms?

Are there any **fleet management** systems used in vehicles? If yes, **how do they work, what types of data are collected, and how is the data stored** (e.g., is the cloud hosting internal to the company or external)? **Can end-users (operators) choose whether to use fleet-management-related features**, or is their use mandatory in the contract?

What is the current industrial opinion about **teleoperation/fully automated operations**? Is it already much in use? What is the **horizon of planning for intense automation in the field**? What are the **main barriers** (e.g., technical, social etc.) for that?

3.5.1 Results of evaluation the baseline for privacy and ethics across the three use cases

Short overview of the answers to the main questions presented in the Table 7.

Table 7: Overview of the industrial baseline evaluation

Question	UC1	UC2	UC3
Does the vehicle collect (or can potentially collect, e.g., the feature exists in the new vehicles but was not present in the older models) some types of information such as:			
GPS data	yes, it is mapping the position with GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System), like GPS, Glonass, Galileo or Baidu	yes	some of the vehicles can map position with GPS, but not the old vehicles
data about the speed of movement and directions of the movement	yes	yes	yes
environmental conditions (like temperature, moisture)	weather condition information coming from station, there is telematic system for temperature update which store no data	no	no
(any) obstacle and terrain information/terrain analysis through sensors or cameras (e.g. position of other objects nearby), borders of operation site	no for terrain analysis, some – for obstacle detection	no	partly, some excavators have cameras

operational efficiency metrics (e.g. fuel usage)	yes	yes, the processes connected to the machine performance	not any of them, but starts to become more popular, helping determine the real use of the vehicle (and prevent personal use situations)
safety-related data (proximity alerts and collision warnings)	In development	the system is not collecting them, just inform operator; but collect collision information	no
If any of that is collected, where and how this information is typically stored ? How long is it usually stored? If there any additional rules for longer storage in case of incidents?	it is stored in the cloud; operating companies makes agreement with the snow groomer developers; there is no specific rules for the information about incidents	no special rules for incident handling, the collision avoidance call given, but not specifically stored; information is storing in the cloud for big companies, smaller companies save the information locally	for now, most operational data are stored in the excavators themselves. It is possible to load this data onto the cloud, but using Wi-Fi can cause network connection issues
How does authorization for vehicle use occur, step-by-step? Where is the authorization data stored ?	anonymised data stored on the vehicle developing company in pseudonymised form (the pseudonymisation should be performed on the operating company side); the keys are stored on operating companies' level	the operating company assigns the individual operator a number. The machine development company only has the operator's number and does not know the identity of the operator.	in many companies there is no specific association between user and vehicle (any operator can use any key to authorise, the area is not very digitalised), however more modern vehicles are identified through login procedures
How is access to the data typically managed ? Have the companies considered scenarios where operators request access to their data (if you ever heard about these types of requests)? If so, what types of data might they ask about?	no information about such requests, data are anonymous for vehicle developing company, theoretically operating company	no information about such requests; companies providing data to terminals (KPIs about the customer operations, fuel level or tyre pressure)	no information about such requests

	can request delete/provide data		
Does the vehicle monitor any vital signals from the operator (e.g. fatigue levels/ alertness through eye tracking)? If yes, where does the information store?	no	no	no
If the operator leaves the company, what usually happens to the data associated with them (e.g., performance data, if they are collected)?	vehicle data are stored; in case of mapping to operator, the standard setting is stored in anonymous version	if any data stored, they are either anonymised (no connection to operator) or pseudonymise (company can relate them to the operator), but by default they are staying in the company	if any data stored, they are either anonymised (no connection to operator) or pseudonymise; they are staying in the company
Have the companies usually implemented any analytical approaches to the data? Do the data used for promotion/salary decision? Do the data use for other purposes , e.g. AI models training ?	yes, but not any personal operator data	yes, the companies can use anonymized data for analysis and training AI; from the operator efficiency metrics side there is not yet requests from the companies about this type of service	use of AI is just starting in the industry, but it is probably the way forward for bigger companies, as it can help with optimization. However, it will not be possible to use this data for promotion decisions, as the trade unions will probably not approve it
If there are any standard consent forms in the industry, explaining the operators GDPR related issues connected to their work, or each company implement their own forms?	no information, happened on the operating company side	for a moment there are initiatives in industry about using common protocols for data sharing, but it is rather on terminal side and its relate to machine data	decided on business level, e.g. there is not yet fully applied data sharing protocols, and all the discussion is related to machine data
Are there any fleet management systems used in vehicles? If yes, how do they work, what types of data	at least some companies implement fleet	It can be useful to coordinate the machine and	it is technically possible and there are several

<p>are collected, and how is the data stored (e.g., is the cloud hosting internal to the company or external)? Can end-users (operators) choose whether to use fleet-management-related features, or is their use mandatory in the contract?</p>	<p>management features, information stored in encrypted cloud, there is no opt-out options</p>	<p>operator; by default, the collected information cannot be switched off</p>	<p>solutions on the market, which aim to coordinate the vehicles; in a moment the system is more to assign vehicle to task and not for coordinating operators. They can call each other if they need coordination</p>
<p>What is the current industrial opinion about teleoperation/fully automated operations? Is it already much in use? What is the horizon of planning for intense automation in the field? What are the main barriers (e.g., technical, social etc.) for that?</p>	<p>still the question for the future, the surrounding is too unpredictable</p>	<p>there are teleoperations in the container handling industry for larger containers (automated terminals) operating machines, but not yet for reach stackers. The surrounding environment and the type of operations performed in the terminal are more difficult to automate compared to autonomous driving</p>	<p>still the question for the future, the surrounding is rather unpredictable (compare to the road, where task for cars is easier to implement)</p>

3.6 Co-design workshop for reevaluating privacy goals and specifying stages of privacy requirements

To assess the achievement of the project’s privacy and ethics goals, we created a synchronous/asynchronous workshop with the stakeholders. Following the paradigm of humanity-centred design, we asked stakeholders not only about the ongoing stages of the project but also about the broader benefits of privacy- and ethics-guided development for society. The procedure included the following steps:

First, we rediscussed privacy requirements proposed in D2.3 in relation to the current specifications of the project development.

Second, we asked participants to think about their developed technologies in relation to requirements. We asked participants to be as detailed as possible and take a narrow perspective (e.g., answering from their perspective as providers of specific technology or holders of specific use cases). We used an online format for the discussion and applied a Mural board for task allocation.

We discussed the following questions:

- The first three questions were about the stages of adopting and applying our privacy requirements in the project: during the project, upon completion, and following completion.
- The next question was formulated towards the industry in general ("How would you like to see this type of requirement being implemented by other companies and the industry in general?")
- The next two questions were made to find case owners, e.g., the persons who will be responsible for the fulfilment of privacy and other ethical goals in the project. This helped create a list of co-dependent actions from the stakeholder side and organise the network of implementations and controls within the project.
- Finally, as we follow the principles of audibility in XR development, proposed by Norval et al. [54] (more information about the paradigm is in D.7.6), we specify the measurable criterion, which will show if we achieved or failed the privacy requirements in the project.

We tested the developed procedure with stakeholders (n=12, including the technology developers and company representatives), and the results showed that the procedure helps to understand the privacy-related questions in the project. We also specified the best possible privacy-related outcomes of this and similar projects for society and industrial ethical XR. However, we found that the procedures for specifying the results of the project are still not clear enough for the participants. Some of them provided too general answers to the question (e.g., "all the results should be in line with the project specification"). Therefore, we decided to align the specification principles with co-evaluation and further development of Privacy Guidelines (more in D7.6)

Table 8: Privacy Requirements goal-setting and roles allocation questions:

How we want it to be implemented mid-term (e.g., September 2024)?
How we want it to be implemented in the final stage of the project?
How we want it to be implemented beyond the frames of the project (e.g., in the industry in the future, what should be a standard for XR augmentation development for the industry)?
Who is responsible for implementing it?
Who is responsible for assessing the implementation?
What are the criteria for successful implementation?
What are the criteria for failure?

3.6.1 Results of co-design workshop for reevaluating privacy goals and specifying stages of privacy requirements

During the privacy requirements elicitation, we performed in the frames of T2.3 (Identification of Privacy Requirements), we formulate seven privacy requirements (PR), which was relevant to the project on that stage:

- (PR1) The uses cases shall identify which personal data are they processing
- (PR2) The use cases shall adopt a data minimization approach
- (PR3) When a privacy threat is discovered, the team developing the use case shall convene to discuss a strategy for mitigating it.

- (PR4) The implementations proposed in the use cases shall have a system in place to modify and delete personal data.
- (PR5) Where the object detection model is in place, the applied algorithm shall be tested for fairness.
- (PR6) Where an object detection system is in place, the vehicle shall display a post or sticker informing about the use of this system.
- (PR7) Where XR-enhanced features are integrated into the system interface, there should be a clear method for users to opt in or opt out.

(More information about it can be found in D2.3).

We found that two of the requirements mentioned in the previous stage of the work, namely PR4 and PR5 are already partly fulfilled by the project, as we chose strict non-data collection approach and opt-in the technologies with embedded fairness (e.g., thermal cameras). However, the discussion showed that stakeholders are unsure whether we should avoid collecting the data completely or share it with operators (e.g., to give them a way to reflect on their daily performance). As this point is a cornerstone of the project for privacy, as it is necessary to make a decision and specify the data collection practice before implementing the tested XR solutions into the following prototype.

We also discussed the use of AI datasets and training set data collection in the project. All the stakeholders agreed that it is important point; we decided not to develop the algorithms (e.g., obstacle detection algorithms) from scratch but to use existing algorithms, fine-tuned with additional data, so the problem of the fairness of the original algorithm appears to be out of the scope. However, this consideration should be kept in mind at the level of results exploitation in the project. The rest of the requirements remain in line with the current steps of project development.

Based on the second stage of the workshop, we create a joint vision of the actions and privacy-and-ethics-related mechanics we should implement in the project:

Table 9: Co-design the privacy and ethics preserving implementations with stakeholders

PR	How we want it to be implemented mid-term (e.g., September 2024)	How we want it to be implemented in the final stage of the project	How we want it to be implemented beyond the frames of the project (e.g., in the industry in the future, what should be a standard for XR augmentation development for the industry)	Who is responsible for implementing it?	Who is responsible for assessing the implementation?	What are the criteria for successful implementation?	What are the criteria for failure?

PR1	<p>Final definition of data collection requests from technology partners;</p> <p>The data determined to collect should be validated through workshop with users (in co-design approach).</p>	<p>Validated list of the privacy and ethics concerns left in the project (based on requirement list);</p> <p>Each concern has actionable way to address (on technology and on interaction level).</p>	<p>Industry-validated guidelines with the best practices and lesson learned from the project for development for similar industry;</p> <p>The considerations should be included in the exploitation plan.</p>	<p>UC leads accumulating result from technology provider</p>	<p>UL partner, end-users; cross-reviewed by developing team</p>	<p>Clear documentation of the data processing which matches the requirements, (b) matches the implementation, satisfies stakeholders and end-users</p>	<p>Unclear requirements, unsatisfied end users (no acceptance of the solutions)</p>
PR2	<p>All technology partners confirm either no collecting personal data or provide the reasons for collecting</p>	<p>Clearly document the data processing pipelines to identify which data are processed, and whether or not they are retained long term</p>	<p>Provide a way to verify that the collection of the personal data is the minimal possible for the implementation to work</p>	<p>UC leads, supported with XR developers</p>	<p>UL partner, UC leads</p>	<p>Confirmation of privacy experts;</p> <p>Data processing matches the requirements.</p>	<p>Unclear what has been stored and why, lack of documentation describing data processing for each feature</p>
PR3	<p>Any researcher/developer discovering a concern should be responsible for bringing it to attention, discussion should be carried out by ethics / privacy lead and project lead + partners responsible for the development of the affected feature; topic should be brought to attention to the whole team and support with Ethics/privacy lead (UL) as soon as possible.</p>	<p>All privacy threats need to be identified. If certain privacy/ethics threats are not solved, they need to be clearly documented</p>	<p>No privacy threats are allowed to be present anymore before bringing it to market;</p> <p>Provide some guidance on how ethical and privacy concerns should be handled (based on the process and learnings in this project), should they arise in subsequent co-design projects or industry development.</p>	<p>The mitigation process is guided by UL, UC-leads and technical experts are part of the team.</p>	<p>Privacy lead, coordinator, UC lead, end-users</p>	<p>Listed identified and resolved concerns validated and approved by stakeholders and end-users</p>	<p>Concerns and issues which stay unresolved/unsatisfactorily resolved to the end of the project</p>

PR4	Currently the development team follow the approach to not collecting the personal data (see more above). However, if the decision about (some) data storage will be justified after the following stage of co-design, we planning to implement the mechanism of control and monitoring which data are collected from operator, for which period of time and how they can be used from operator and company side.						
PR5	Currently developers are planning to use only preexisting algorithms (see more above), however in any case the algorithms will be tested according to use case specification to assure the absence of the performance problem.						
PR6	Project should have preliminary decision how and when present the warnings (some use cases already propose their ideas of placement and structure of warnings)	Create the warning system using automation transparency principles	Develop clear guidelines for presenting the warnings in case of Off-Highway Machinery	Systems provider, Site operator	Safety inspector (the implementation would be mostly on operation side)	Clear and understandable warning (rested with end-users)	Unclear non-accessible information
PR7	Describe which features are can/can't be opt in/opt out. Several partners already confirmed the mechanism is implemented in their solutions	All solutions should be considered and decided which benefit from the possibility to opt in/out.	Before bringing it to the market, the possibility to opt in/out should be available for all technologies that make sense to include this feature.	UC Leads, Technology developers	Technology developers, co-design and privacy leads	User feedback, confirmation of privacy experts	Unclear requirements, unsatisfied end users (operators reject the solutions)

The results of the workshop helped formulate the list of short, mid, and long-term goals in privacy and ethics for the project. Our next step will be to hold the next workshop in the series in line with continuation of Privacy Guidelines development

3.7 Quantitative methods for assessment of privacy and ethical concerns

Based on the project goals and processes we specified the following quantitative measures:

3.7.1 The baseline questionnaires for general privacy perception

The previous studies shows that people are significantly vary in terms of their general perception of privacy in human-computer interaction [47]. Therefore, it is important to establish a baseline in evaluations to be

able disentangle the amount concerns, provided by XR system with person's level of concerns about privacy. In the evaluations we used the following baselines:

- **Internet Users' Information Privacy Concerns (IUIPC) questionnaire** about general concerns for privacy online. The IUIPC is established validated instrument, designed to measure privacy concerns on 3 dimensions: collection (how much person concerned about amount of data collected by external parties for their benefit), control (how much person wants to have control over their personal data) and awareness about data gathering practices[47].
- As alternative approach, proposing more in depth evaluation of concerns towards vertical (authority-related) and horizontal (other social connections), we applied the **Online Privacy Concerns Scale by Masur [49]**. We used this version of a baseline in the online evaluation, as we specifically wanted to investigate the moderation effect of vertical privacy concerns on perception of the data storage on the company side.

3.7.2 The implementation-related privacy concerns

- **UEQ+, Scale Trust, Trustworthiness of Content.** The original User Experience Questionnaire [42], developed by is based on the theoretical model of hedonic and utilitarian values of the product, proposed by Hassenzahl [33]; however, the instrument is constructed to be able to incorporate additional modules for the extensive investigation; the chosen Trust and Trustworthiness of content scale was validated and extensively used in UEQ+ approach.
- **UPSP privacy scale (selected, but discarded).** The second proposed questionnaire, developed by Ayalon and Toch [7], is dedicated to evaluating users' perceptions about a system's privacy in the aspects of perceived information control, confidentiality, importance of information transparency, secondary usage, data deletion, perceived privacy risk, information sensitivity, protection strategies, identity sharing. The questions' structure allows the questionnaire's tailor to evaluate specific systems or applications [7]. We planned to apply the scale to measure the effects of XR evaluation to privacy and security of implementations; however the current discussion inside the development team results in the deletion of the scale from the setting by two reasons: the scale has 27 questions, which make it overly detailed for feature-by-feature evaluation, and the second - it very much centred on personal information; however following by the privacy considerations embedded into the project we always opted in for solutions which not collected privacy information. Therefore, we decided to substitute this questionnaire by the following:
- **Mobile users' information privacy concerns (MUIPC) for XR implementations** We choose MUIPC scale for making quick evaluation of the privacy perception in the tasks, performed in the use cases. The scale was developed by [80] for measuring mobile users concerns and is largely used beyond just the domain of mobile technologies (e.g., IoT [23]). The scale is loosely based on IUIPC, but have different dimensions: concerns about perceived surveillance from technology, perceived intrusion and secondary use of the information. The scale has 9 items (3 for each dimension).
- The baseline (ME-work) and ethics-related in-use case measurement (UEQ+ scales for positive user experience and self-efficacy are described in D3.10).

4 Conclusion

Developing technologies that are sensitive to user privacy and do not create additional risks to ethics on workplace is serious challenge. Previous works showed that the use of XR technologies creates risks to users' privacy and security and not prone to bad designing practices (e.g. deceptive designs [31]). Putting XR into the context of work add specific risks, connected to work ethics (e.g., disturbing practices of physical data collection or limiting users' agency).

Taking VSD lenses we adopted and developed methods to address stakeholders' and users' values and privacy requests. We tested procedures with stakeholders and end users, and the received insights have helped us further co-design and evaluate prototypes of the solutions.

The results of this deliverable are as follow:

- Selection and adaptation of different qualitative and quantitative methods to support the evaluation process.
- Design and empirical evaluation of the first questionnaire to measure ethical and privacy concerns in industrial XR development.

They can be used in the following ways:

- To empirically inform the guidelines we are developing for the domain of off-highway machinery (the final version of the guidelines is presented in D7.6).
- To methodologically inform the evaluation of privacy and ethics, presented in D6.7.
- To bring the discovered ethical and privacy concerns to the stakeholders and end users in the following cycles of prototype development.
- To make the road for the future development of quantitative and qualitative methods for assessing Industrial XR solutions beyond the project.

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ABBREVIATIONS / ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
HCD	Humanity-Centred Design
M	Mean
PVQ40	Portrait Values Questionnaire
SVS	Schwartz Value Survey
SD	Standard Deviation
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UC	Use Case
VAM	Value-Based Adoption Model
VR	Virtual Reality
VSD	Value-Sensitive Design
XR	Extended Reality